

Title

Response of numbers of heterozygous loci in hybrids to parental dominant allele accumulation

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Abstract

Hybrid yield depends on heterosis and parental yields. Heterosis benefits from heterozygous loci in hybrids; parental improvement reflects dominant allele accumulation. However, how the numbers of heterozygous loci respond to this accumulation remains unclear. Our theoretical study shows that as dominant alleles accumulate in parents, the numbers of heterozygous loci first increase and then decrease in the hybrids, each possessing the highest number of heterozygous loci at a different accumulation level. This trend may explain phenomena related to elite hybrids and, together with these phenomena, suggests that with continuous parental improvement, the upper limits of heterosis may decrease after increasing. A decrease in heterosis may not be fully compensated for by an increase in parental yields. If so, contributions from heterosis and parental yields should be appropriately manipulated to enhance elite hybrid yields.

INTRODUCTION

Heterosis refers to the superiority of an F₁ hybrid over its inbred parents (1, 2). The discovery of heterosis in maize, along with the growth in knowledge about the basis of heredity, initiated the exploitation of heterosis in plants (1, 3–6). The genetic circumvention of self-fertilization in female lines led to the success of hybrid seed production in some self-pollinated species, such as rice (7–10). Today, about half of the global production of maize and rice, two of the world's most important crops, is from hybrid seeds (1, 7, 8, 10–13).

The three classical hypotheses have been advanced to explain heterosis (14–21). The dominance hypothesis attributes heterosis to the suppression of deleterious recessives from one parent by dominant alleles from the other (14, 18–21). The overdominance hypothesis assumes that the heterozygote is superior to either homozygote at key loci (15, 16, 18–21). The epistasis hypothesis postulates that certain non-allelic gene interactions have favorable effects (17–21). Over the last two decades, advances in genomics and molecular biology have enabled researchers to identify specific genes and pathways involved in heterosis; hence, new hypotheses have been proposed (2, 22–25). The gene balance hypothesis posits that an optimal stoichiometric balance among members of multisubunit complexes, as a result of kinetics and mode of assembly, enhances the function of the whole in hybrids (2, 22, 23). The unifying theory emphasizes that hybrids reduce the production of defective proteins, thereby providing enough energy for cell division and growth (24). The HoIIB model argues that functions can be activated because of a sufficient background in hybrids (25). On the basis of all these explanations, heterosis benefits from heterozygous loci in hybrids (2, 14–25).

Yield is the key determinant of food security (1, 7, 10). The primary goal of hybrid breeding is to enhance hybrid yields (1, 7, 10). A hybrid's yield depends on both heterosis and the yields of its inbred parents (1, 7, 10). Heterosis benefits from heterozygous loci in hybrids (2, 14–25), whereas inbred improvement reflects the accumulation of dominant alleles (2, 7, 22, 23, 26). However, how the numbers of heterozygous loci in hybrids respond to the accumulation of dominant alleles in their parents remains unclear. This question is nearly impossible or at least very difficult to address experimentally due to practical and technical limitations as well as the complexities of yield (13, 27–30).

Focusing on diploid plants, we present a theoretical study illustrating how the numbers of heterozygous loci in hybrids respond to the accumulation of dominant alleles in their parents. Our results show that as dominant alleles accumulate in parents, the numbers of heterozygous loci first increase and then decrease in the ideal hybrids, each possessing the highest number of heterozygous loci at a different level of accumulation. This trend may explain phenomena observed in elite hybrids (achieved through breeding practices and reflecting the success of breeding efforts) and their parents. Together, the trend and these phenomena suggest that with continuous parental improvement, the upper limits of heterosis may decrease after increasing. A decrease in heterosis may not be fully compensated for by an increase in parental yields, which may imply a decrease in the upper limits of hybrid yields. If so, the contributions from heterosis and parental yields should be appropriately manipulated to enhance yields of elite hybrids.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

All possible numbers of heterozygous loci in hybrids

Let n be the number of loci related to yield. To illustrate how the numbers of heterozygous loci in hybrids respond to the accumulation of dominant alleles in their parents, and to demonstrate the role of n in both this response and the accumulation, we assume $n = 30$ or $n = 35$, although the actual value of n is expected to be relatively stable and considerably higher than these assumed values. Some dominant alleles were fixed as a result of both natural and artificial selection before and during domestication (31, 32). To show the whole process of the response to the accumulation, we assume that no fixed genes exist.

Let x be the number of loci with dominant alleles in one parent, and let y be the number of loci with dominant alleles in the other. Without loss of generality, we assume $x \geq y$. $x - y$ may vary across different hybrids in hybrid breeding practices; however, this variation cannot be fully captured in a theoretical framework. To demonstrate the influence of $x - y$ on both the response and the accumulation, we use three values, namely $x - y = 0$, $x - y = 5$, and $x - y = 10$, for each of which the response to the accumulation is illustrated (Fig. 1).

Let h be the number of heterozygous loci in the F_1 . Let h_{\min} and h_{\max} be the lowest and highest values among all possible values of h associated with a value of $x + y$. For each value of $x + y$, we determine h_{\min} and h_{\max} , and then generate all possible values of h (Fig. 1 and Materials and Methods).

We use these three values of $x - y$ to illustrate h in response to the increase in $x + y$, thereby demonstrating the influence of $x - y$ on both h and $x + y$ (Fig. 1). Building on this, h_{\min} depends on $x - y$, as $h_{\min} = x - y$ (Fig. 1 and Materials and Methods). In addition, the influence of $x - y$ on both the key values of h_{\max} and the corresponding key values of $x + y$ is as follows: (i) h_{\max} starts at $(x - y) + 2$ when $x + y$ starts at $(x - y) + 2$; (ii) h_{\max} peaks at n when $x + y$ is centered at n , if n and $x - y$ have the same parity; (iii) h_{\max} peaks at $n - 1$ when $x + y$ is centered on $n - 1$ and $n + 1$, if n and $x - y$ have opposite parity; and (iv) h_{\max} ends at $(x - y) + 2$ when $x + y$, which ends at $2n - (x - y)$, reaches $2n - [(x - y) + 2]$ (Fig. 1 and Materials and Methods). In short, the starting, peak, and ending values of h_{\max} depend on $x - y$, n , and $x - y$, respectively, whereas the starting, central, and ending values of $x + y$ depend on $x - y$, n , and both $2n$ and $x - y$. Taken together, since n and/or $x - y$ determine h_{\min} and the key values of both h_{\max} and $x + y$ through these particular ways as described above, the gap between n and $x - y$ governs the relative stability of the overall pattern shaped by h_{\min} and these key values (Fig. 1). Consequently, as long as the gap between n and $x - y$ is large enough, the variation in $x - y$ across different hybrids does not substantially alter the overall pattern of h in response to the increase in $x + y$ (Fig. 1). In other words, the variation in the difference in the number of loci with dominant alleles between two parents across different hybrids does not substantially alter the overall pattern of how the numbers of heterozygous loci in hybrids respond to the accumulation of dominant alleles in their parents (Fig. 1).

Hybrids with low numbers of heterozygous loci

At nearly every value of $x + y$, there are h values that are not close to h_{\max} ; as $x + y$ increases, the numbers of such h values first increase and then decrease (the blue and black dots not close to the red dots in Fig. 1). In addition, as $x + y$ increases, h_{\min} remains unchanged for each

of the three values of $x - y$, but varies across these values (the black dots in Fig. 1). These results are interpreted to mean that (i) hybrids with low numbers of heterozygous loci always have a chance to be generated regardless of the numbers of dominant alleles in parents; and (ii) this chance of generating hybrids with low numbers of heterozygous loci increases as the accumulation of dominant alleles in parents approaches the midpoint (both the blue dots not close to the red dots and the black dots in Fig. 1).

Several related phenomena observed in hybrid breeding practices are as follows: (i) crosses between pairs of parents with relatively high yields might exhibit weak heterosis; (ii) parental yields could not be used to predict heterosis; and (iii) the correlation between parental yields and heterosis was rather poor (1, 7, 10). These phenomena may be explained by our result: regardless of the numbers of dominant alleles in parents, hybrids with low numbers of heterozygous loci always have a chance to be generated (both the blue dots not close to the red dots and the black dots in Fig. 1). Thus, it may be stated that regardless of the levels of parental improvement, hybrids exhibiting weak heterosis always had a chance to be generated (1, 7, 10).

This weak heterosis (1, 7, 10) may be explained by the low numbers of heterozygous loci in hybrids, and such hybrids always have a chance to be generated (both the blue dots not close to the red dots and the black dots in Fig. 1); hence, to minimize the chance of generating such hybrids, the numbers of heterozygous loci should be estimated or predicted before hybrids are generated. Thus, it is recommended to employ available strategies for parental selection and to optimize these strategies as much as possible with advances in science and technology. In addition, it should be emphasized that as the accumulation of dominant alleles in parents approaches the midpoint, the chance of generating hybrids with low numbers of heterozygous loci increases (both the blue dots not close to the red dots and the black dots in Fig. 1). Thus, using efficient strategies for parental selection becomes particularly important.

Hybrids with high numbers of heterozygous loci

Increase in numbers of heterozygous loci

h_{\max} increases as $x + y$ increases before $x + y$ reaches n or $n \pm 1$ (the red dots before the midpoint in Fig. 1). In other words, before the sum of loci with dominant alleles in both parents reaches the midpoint, as dominant alleles accumulate in parents, the numbers of heterozygous loci increase in the ideal hybrids, each possessing the highest number of heterozygous loci at a different level of accumulation (the red dots before the midpoint in Fig. 1). At nearly every value of $x + y$, there are h values that are close to h_{\max} (the blue dots close to the red dots in Fig. 1). In other words, at nearly every level of accumulation of dominant alleles in parents, there are hybrids whose numbers of heterozygous loci are close to the highest (the blue dots close to the red dots in Fig. 1). These hybrids (the blue dots close to the red dots in Fig. 1) better represent the outcomes of breeding practices than the ideal hybrids (the red dots in Fig. 1).

The first maize inbreds were isolated from open-pollinated varieties at the beginning of the twentieth century and had poor yields (1, 3). The poor yields of the first maize inbreds may be explained by the low numbers of dominant alleles (the initial portion of the $x + y$ values in Fig. 1). The breeding efforts aimed at enhancing the yields of the elite maize hybrids (1, 33–

46) led to the increases in both the heterosis and the yields of their parents (1, 34, 36, 37) (Fig. 2). The increase in the heterosis exhibited by the elite maize hybrids and the increase in the yields of their parents may be explained by the increase in the numbers of heterozygous loci and the accumulation of dominant alleles (the red and nearby blue dots before the midpoint in Fig. 1).

For the two contributors to hybrid yields, both the heterosis exhibited by the elite maize hybrids and the yields of their parents increased (1, 34, 36, 37) (Fig. 2). This phenomenon indicates that crosses between pairs of highly improved parents have a chance to generate elite hybrids exhibiting stronger heterosis and consequently higher yields than those from poorly improved parents. Therefore, it is recommended to accelerate inbred improvement and consistently use newly improved inbreds as parents.

Decrease in numbers of heterozygous loci

h_{\max} decreases as $x + y$ increases after $x + y$ reaches n or $n \pm 1$ (the red dots after the midpoint in Fig. 1). In other words, after the sum of loci with dominant alleles in both parents reaches the midpoint, as dominant alleles continue to accumulate in parents, the numbers of heterozygous loci decrease in the ideal hybrids, each possessing the highest number of heterozygous loci at a different level of accumulation (the red dots after the midpoint in Fig. 1).

The elite rice hybrids exhibited weak heterosis (5, 7, 10, 47–50), and their parents possessed high yields as a result of both unintentional and intentional selection over millennia of traditional farming and modern breeding (7, 10, 32, 51). The weak heterosis exhibited by the elite rice hybrids and the high yields of their parents may be explained by the insufficient numbers of heterozygous loci and the sufficient numbers of dominant alleles (the final portion of the red and nearby blue dots in Fig. 1).

In maize, the heterosis exhibited by the elite hybrids increased, and the yields of their parents increased from the very low levels after the first inbreds were isolated from open-pollinated varieties at the beginning of the twentieth century (1, 3, 34, 36, 37) (Fig. 2). In rice, the elite hybrids exhibited the weak heterosis (5, 7, 10, 47–50), and their parents possessed the high yields as a result of both unintentional and intentional selection over millennia of traditional farming and modern breeding (7, 10, 32, 51). The gap in these phenomena observed between maize and rice (1, 3, 5, 7, 10, 32, 34, 36, 37, 47–51) (Fig. 2) may be bridged by a decrease in heterosis coupled with continuous parental improvement. These phenomena thus raise the possibility that with continuous parental improvement, the upper limits of heterosis may decrease after increasing. A decrease in the upper limits of heterosis and continuous parental improvement may be attributable to the decrease in the numbers of heterozygous loci and the continuous accumulation of dominant alleles (the red and nearby blue dots after the midpoint in Fig. 1).

For the two contributors to hybrid yields, the upper limits of heterosis may decrease, whereas parental yields increase (see above). The dominance hypothesis suggests that a decrease in heterosis may be compensated for by an increase in parental yields (5, 7, 8, 10), which may imply that the upper limits of hybrid yields are not undermined. If so, accelerating inbred improvement and consistently using newly improved inbreds as parents (see above) would

remain recommended, and elite inbreds would eventually match elite hybrids (5, 7, 8, 10). However, because growing evidence suggests that the dominance hypothesis is only one of several non-mutually exclusive hypotheses explaining heterosis (2, 14–25), the decrease in heterosis may not be fully compensated for by the increase in parental yields, which may imply a decrease in the upper limits of hybrid yields. If so, the contributions from heterosis and parental yields should be appropriately manipulated to enhance yields of elite hybrids.

Elite maize hybrids

The increase in the heterosis exhibited by the elite maize hybrids and the increase in the yields of their parents (1, 34, 36, 37) (Fig. 2) may be explained by the increase in the numbers of heterozygous loci and the accumulation of dominant alleles (the red and nearby blue dots before the midpoint in Fig. 1). As dominant alleles continue to accumulate in parents, the numbers of heterozygous loci in elite maize hybrids may approach their peak (the red and nearby blue dots around the midpoint in Fig. 1). Correspondingly, with continuous parental improvement, heterosis exhibited by elite maize hybrids may also approach its peak. Subsequently, a decrease in the upper limits of heterosis may occur with continuous parental improvement and may not be fully compensated for by an increase in parental yields, which may imply a decrease in the upper limits of hybrid yields (see above). If so, the potential decrease in the upper limits of hybrid yields could be avoided as long as breeding efforts remain focused on enhancing yields of elite maize hybrids. Thus, elite maize hybrids would continue to exhibit near-peak heterosis and would continue to be generated from crosses between pairs of parents with moderate levels of improvement (see above). Correspondingly, elite maize hybrids would possess near-peak numbers of heterozygous loci and would be generated from crosses between pairs of parents with moderate levels of accumulation of dominant alleles (the red and nearby blue dots around the midpoint in Fig. 1).

Elite rice hybrids

The weak heterosis exhibited by the elite rice hybrids (5, 7, 10, 47–50) and the high yields of their parents (7, 10, 32, 51) may be explained by the insufficient numbers of heterozygous loci and the sufficient numbers of dominant alleles (the final portion of the red and nearby blue dots in Fig. 1). On the basis of these phenomena and these explanations, strong heterosis might not have had a chance to be exhibited, likely due to the consistent use of highly improved inbreds as parents. This lack of strong heterosis may not be fully compensated for by high parental yields, which may imply a decrease in the upper limits of hybrid yields (see above). If so, to enhance yields of elite rice hybrids, crosses between pairs of parents with moderate levels of improvement should be made, as such crosses would not only ensure an appropriate contribution from parental yields but also have a chance to exhibit near-peak heterosis (see above). Correspondingly, crosses between pairs of parents with moderate levels of accumulation of dominant alleles would have a chance to generate elite rice hybrids with near-peak numbers of heterozygous loci (the red and nearby blue dots around the midpoint in Fig. 1). Alternatively, crosses between pairs of parents with different levels of accumulation of dominant alleles would also have a chance to generate elite rice hybrids with near-peak numbers of heterozygous loci, as long as the levels of accumulation in both parents are approximately symmetric with respect to the midpoint of accumulation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Starting, central, and ending values of $x + y$

n is the number of loci related to yield. We assume $n = 30$ or $n = 35$. We assume that no fixed genes exist. x is the number of loci with dominant alleles in one parent, and y is the number of loci with dominant alleles in the other. We assume $x \geq y$. $x - y = 0$, $x - y = 5$, and $x - y = 10$ are three values of $x - y$.

At the starting points of $x + y$, because $y \leq x$, $y = 1$, $x = (x - y) + 1$, and $x + y = (x - y) + 1 + 1 = (x - y) + 2$. At the central points of $x + y$, $x + y = n$ when n and $x - y$ have the same parity, whereas $x + y = n - 1$ and $x + y = n + 1$ when n and $x - y$ have opposite parity. At the ending points of $x + y$, because $x \geq y$, $x = n$, $y = n - (x - y)$, and $x + y = n + n - (x - y) = 2n - (x - y)$.

For example, for $n = 30$ and $x - y = 10$, the starting value of $x + y$ is $(x - y) + 2 = 10 + 2 = 12$, the central value of $x + y$ is $n = 30$, and the ending value of $x + y$ is $2n - (x - y) = 2 \times 30 - 10 = 50$.

As another example, for $n = 30$ and $x - y = 5$, the starting value of $x + y$ is $(x - y) + 2 = 5 + 2 = 7$, the central values of $x + y$ are $n - 1 = 30 - 1 = 29$ and $n + 1 = 30 + 1 = 31$, and the ending value of $x + y$ is $2n - (x - y) = 2 \times 30 - 5 = 55$.

h_{\min} , h_{\max} , and all possible values of h

h is the number of heterozygous loci in the F_1 . h_{\min} and h_{\max} are the lowest and highest values among all possible values of h associated with a value of $x + y$.

For a value of $x + y$, there are numerous hybrid combinations. In one such hybrid combination, y dominant alleles from one parent, combined with y dominant alleles from the other, form y homozygous dominant alleles in the F_1 , and $x - y$ dominant alleles from the former, combined with $x - y$ recessive alleles from the latter, form $x - y$ heterozygous loci in the F_1 . Hence, h reaches h_{\min} , and $h_{\min} = x - y$.

This value of $x + y$ falls into one of two cases: $x + y \leq n$ or $x + y \geq n$.

If this value of $x + y$ falls into the case of $x + y \leq n$, in one such hybrid combination, all dominant alleles from both parents pair with recessive alleles to form heterozygous loci in the F_1 . Hence, h reaches h_{\max} , and $h_{\max} = x + y$.

Thus, for hybrid combinations with $x + y \leq n$, $x - y \leq h \leq x + y$. For example, for $n = 30$ and $x = 15$, $x - y = 10$ represents $x = 15$ and $y = 5$; because $x + y = 15 + 5 = 20$ and $n = 30$, $x + y < n$, and thus $x - y \leq h \leq x + y$; and as $x - y = 10$ and $x + y = 20$, $h = 10, 12, 14, 16, \dots, 20$.

If this value of $x + y$ falls into the case of $x + y \geq n$, we may imagine that in one such hybrid combination, dominant alleles from both parents first pair with recessive alleles to form n heterozygous loci in the F_1 , and $x + y - n$ dominant alleles from both parents then convert heterozygous loci to homozygous dominant alleles in the F_1 . Hence, h reaches h_{\max} , and $h_{\max} = n - (x + y - n) = 2n - (x + y)$.

Thus, for hybrid combinations with $x + y \geq n$, $x - y \leq h \leq 2n - (x + y)$. For example, for $n = 30$ and $x = 22$, $x - y = 5$ represents $x = 22$ and $y = 17$; because $x + y = 22 + 17 = 39$ and $n = 30$, $x + y > n$, and thus $x - y \leq h \leq 2n - (x + y)$; and as $x - y = 5$ and $2n - (x + y) = 2 \times 30 - 39 = 21$, $h = 5, 7, 9, 11, \dots, 21$.

Starting, peak, and ending values of h_{\max}

$h_{\max} = x + y$ when $x + y \leq n$, whereas $h_{\max} = 2n - (x + y)$ when $x + y \geq n$. On the basis of these expressions and these corresponding values of $x + y$, the starting, peak, and ending values of h_{\max} can be derived.

The starting value of h_{\max} corresponds to $x + y = (x - y) + 2$. Because $x + y = (x - y) + 2 \leq n$, $h_{\max} = x + y = (x - y) + 2$. Thus, the starting value of h_{\max} is $(x - y) + 2$.

The peak value of h_{\max} corresponds to $x + y = n$ when n and $x - y$ have the same parity. Because $x + y = n$, $h_{\max} = x + y = n$ or $h_{\max} = 2n - (x + y) = 2n - n = n$. Thus, the peak value of h_{\max} is n when n and $x - y$ have the same parity.

The peak value of h_{\max} corresponds to $x + y = n - 1$ and $x + y = n + 1$ when n and $x - y$ have opposite parity. When $x + y = n - 1$, because $x + y = n - 1 < n$, $h_{\max} = x + y = n - 1$. When $x + y = n + 1$, because $x + y = n + 1 > n$, $h_{\max} = 2n - (x + y) = 2n - (n + 1) = n - 1$. Thus, the peak value of h_{\max} is $n - 1$ when n and $x - y$ have opposite parity.

The ending value of h_{\max} corresponds to $x + y = 2n - [(x - y) + 2]$. Because $x + y = 2n - [(x - y) + 2] \geq n$, $h_{\max} = 2n - (x + y) = 2n - \{2n - [(x - y) + 2]\} = (x - y) + 2$. Thus, the ending value of h_{\max} is $(x - y) + 2$.

For example, for $n = 30$ and $x - y = 10$, the starting value of h_{\max} is $(x - y) + 2 = 10 + 2 = 12$, the peak value of h_{\max} is $n = 30$, and the ending value of h_{\max} is $(x - y) + 2 = 10 + 2 = 12$.

As another example, for $n = 30$ and $x - y = 5$, the starting value of h_{\max} is $(x - y) + 2 = 5 + 2 = 7$, the peak value of h_{\max} is $n - 1 = 30 - 1 = 29$, and the ending value of h_{\max} is $(x - y) + 2 = 5 + 2 = 7$.

Maize experiment

In the maize experiment, 42 hybrids were divided into six groups, and each group included seven hybrids generated on the basis of the pedigrees of the elite hybrids released during one of the six decades (the 1930s through the 1980s) (1, 34, 36, 37). These hybrids and their parents were grown together in bordered plots at three plant densities across three locations in 1992 and two locations in 1993, and were evaluated for yield (1, 34, 36, 37).

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Fig. 1. Response of h to increase in $x + y$. n is the number of loci related to yield. $n = 30$ or $n = 35$ is assumed. Fixed genes are assumed to be nonexistent. x is the number of loci with dominant alleles in one parent, and y is the number of loci with dominant alleles in the other. $x \geq y$ is assumed. $x - y = 0$, $x - y = 5$, and $x - y = 10$ are three values of $x - y$. h is the number of heterozygous loci in the F_1 . Each of the red, blue, and black dots denotes a value of h corresponding to a value of $x + y$. h_{\min} and h_{\max} are the lowest and highest values among all possible values of h associated with a value of $x + y$. Each black dot denotes a value of h_{\min} , and each red dot denotes a value of h_{\max} .

Fig. 2. Changes in F₁ yield, midparent yield, and heterosis for yield. In the maize experiment, 42 hybrids were divided into six groups, and each group included seven hybrids generated on the basis of the pedigrees of the elite hybrids released during one of the six decades (the 1930s through the 1980s) (1, 34, 36, 37). Each dot represents the average of a group of hybrid combinations over two years, two or three locations per year, and three plant densities per location (1, 34, 36, 37). Heterosis is calculated as the difference between F₁ yield and midparent yield.